

Appendix: Sample of the code book for “Collaborative nature in managing requirements changes”

	Raw data	Code	Concept	Category
Meeting 01	<p>P3: Well. Do you mind if I request you to work with P4 on this one day?</p> <p>P8: Yep, we are going to have a look at it definitely. (for P4), let’s plan a time for both of us.</p> <p>P4: Awesome.</p>	Cooperation (among team)	<p align="center">Collaboration work (to complete changes)</p>	<p align="center">Collaborative nature in managing requirements changes</p>
Meeting 04	<p>P5: I’m wrapping up the testing for ... part. By the end of this week, it should be done. So, (for P8), can we plan the integration next week? Are you ok with that?</p> <p>P8: Probably somewhere around next Wednesday would be fine.</p>	Working together to complete task		
Meeting 06	<p>P3: I think we can definitely talk about this with the product owner and see what he says, and if yes, this can be incorporated, then probably we'll have to look at the priority in a different manner as long as the product owner and the team are happy. So, is there any team collaboration that we need for this work? Or is this just more like something that the front and developers want to keep in?</p> <p>P9: we might want to go through them at the storytime. <i>Then maybe we can decide. I am happy to work on it.</i></p>	Providing support to do changes (for the team)		
Meeting 15	<p>P2: There are two stories that we need to focus on. (P1), informed about this after his meeting with (X stakeholder).</p> <p>P10: The other one, 2550 one, I started working on it. I am also testing some cases with P8 and P9. I think we can look into that as well.</p> <p>P8: Let’s begin the preparation for the X feature as well (to P10); what do you say? I’m also working on the automation piece in the background; I can work on it with you</p> <p>P10: Yep, then we can have a look at it definitely and see how it goes. I think we can work on it</p>	Collaborative work (to complete added tasks)		
Meeting 18	<p>P1: The other issue (to P10), correct me if I’m wrong, but with the (feature Y), we are still doing sample testing, right? The (X stakeholder) has not released the (data) yet.</p> <p>P10: Yes, not yet</p> <p>P1: I don’t really want to cancel it because you have already made the change as they wanted. But we have been trying to get them. It will be more pain to keep it last.</p>	Support to keep the changes		

	<p>P3: I will talk to them today to get (data) soon.</p> <p>P1: Great (to P8); just keep it to change the values. Make sure that it functions right or just leave it until we get the (data)</p> <p>P8: Okay, thanks (to P3), we can work on it after your update then</p>			
Meeting 19	<p>P11: This is related to 2905; I ran a test yesterday. It was successful. But with the new XXX allocation and integration (to P8 & P9), can you make one more run today? Then, we will see how we go with that.</p> <p>P8: (to P11), yes, we can do it in our meeting after this one. Sounds good? (to P9), can you join? It's XXX allocation validation. It's basically testing these two things together.</p> <p>P9: Yes, But I have a discussion with P1 after this meeting. I can go through it after this.</p> <p>P8: Okay, we can discuss it later today then.</p>	Cooperative to complete tasks		
Meeting 22	<p>P9: On 2549, I further need some help to progress. P2 and I discussed this earlier. (to P10), will be able to have a look at it? It is this XX part that we had to add in the last sprint.</p> <p>P10: Yep, I think we (mentioning P4) did that part. When do you want it to be done (P9)?</p> <p>P9: By tomorrow?</p> <p>P10: I'll try, (to P1), do we have an ETA from (X stakeholder) about when will that they probably be able to send the (data)? If it is going to be late, I can work on this with P9 today.</p> <p>P1: Not yet, it's taking time, I guess</p> <p>P10: Okay, please let me know</p>	Support others to complete new changes		
Meeting 23	<p>P1: While we are talking about 2551, make sure not to mix it up with the request of the validation in back end (XXX feature). Based on the time in this sprint, we can move it to the next sprint.</p> <p>P4: Could we keep it as it is at the moment?</p> <p>P1: Yes, we are not touching that at all. It will take more time. For the next sprint, I want (P10, P4 & P5) to have a closer look at it. If not just keep it.</p> <p>P10: We are going to add (name) allocation anyway. Lots of stuff is there to do. We can look at it while doing that, of course in the next sprint.</p> <p>P4: Yes, it is just that we need to use the schedule properly, without repeating. I think we might be able to do it just by changing (anonymised).</p>	Collaboration work on new tasks		

Meeting 26	<p>P1: Someone will bring this up in the next (stakeholder) meeting. We need to get this resolved.</p> <p>P2: Yes, I can do that. It is (stakeholder) who requested this. I think we need to talk to them.</p> <p>P9: So the (data) will be changed, right? Could I test with the current data we have? Or else, I have to put this on hold and I think we are missing the start of testing everything end to end</p> <p>P1: Yes, yesterday P8 and I worked on the front end part to the back end enhancement. So what was happening was that our errors were not detailed enough to see what was wrong with the changes.</p> <p>P2: In the integration piece, there was a missing element in the sessional locations response. I think that little minor things that help us improve the ratio between UI and the back end.</p> <p>P8: I think we are missing that because we are missing that story. We have to work on the issues of this change to make the integration smooth. So, I guess it'd be great if I work with P2, and P9 on this within next couple of days.</p> <p>P9: I agree. We have to prioritize this</p>	Collaborative work to solve the issues (on changes)		
P1/INT01	<p>"I can think of one example. Generally, junior members tend to observe and learn. But whenever there are new changes to be made, which are difficult to handle, they want someone's support to work on it. I think there are couple of people in my team, who understand this and they are always offer their support to solve it. I think it is because of their nature"</p>	Nature of working together (to make changes)		
P2/INT02	<p>"There are a couple of factors I think are important. Specifically, the cooperation among team members, I have seen in our team that most of them are very helpful to each other. I joined the team as a junior member, and they helped me a lot when dealing with different requests from (anonymised) and then changing our sprint plans accordingly."</p>	Cooperative team members		
P3/INT03	<p>"I think it is really helpful to have cooperative team members when we prioritize the requirements and handle requirement changes in a later phase. In the end, it is all about teamwork"</p>	Cooperative team members in handling changes		

P4/INT04	"I have seen how engaging my team members are. When it is more engaging, it is more fun, effective and you don't feel the difficulties. It's like we'll go through it. Whether it is deadlines, change requests, or anything, as a team coming up with solutions together. Having such team members make the difference"	Engaging team members		
P7/INT06	"There was a person who was working on time, you know, only eight to five working hours, he is not picking any phone calls after that. But, when he works, he is very efficient; he knows how to work with others, complete the tasks beforehand and even handle most of the changes. I think that his organizing and cooperative traits are really helpful"	Cooperative trait of the team member		

Sample of a memo on "Collaborative nature of Team members"

During the meetings, P8 and P10 seem to have mostly engaged with team members compared to others. They always work together and even mostly with P9. Among the follow-up interview participants, the majority (n=5) talked about the collaborative nature and how it is helpful in completing their tasks. This is specifically observed in the meetings when they are discussing new user stories, changes they have to make or testing the changes they made. They refer to it as "supportive team members", "cooperation", "working together", and "coping with others", which emphasise the collaborative nature of the individual. This can be identified as a personality-related characteristic. In the follow-up interview, P1, P2, P3, P4 and P6 discussed this and highlighted that their collaborative nature positively impacted their task completion, specifically working on requirements changes. However, it would be great to know their opinion from P8 and P10, who seem to be highly collaborative but who did not participate in our follow-up interviews.